

1 **Recent advances in the processing of green tea biomolecules**
2 **using ethyl lactate. A review**

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18

19Abstract

20Background

21Green tea and its decaffeinated products are foodstuffs which focus a great commercial
22attention due to their interesting healthy properties. Catechins are the main phenolic
23compounds in tea leaves and these are receiving considerable interest due to their
24potential benefits on human health. In this sense, many studies have been performed
25with the aim of removing the caffeine and obtaining either decaffeinated green tea
26leaves preserving the catechins or decaffeinated catechins-rich extracts.

27Scope and Approach

28In this review, different methods and solvents described in the literature for green tea
29decaffeination and recovery of high valued catechins are revised. Particular attention is
30given to ethyl lactate, an agrochemical green solvent studied for the extraction of
31caffeine for the first time.

32Key Findings and Conclusions

33A diversity of results has been reported for the different green solvents and extraction
34techniques studied to remove caffeine from green tea leaves and extracts in the last
35years. Nevertheless, despite the solvent used, the loss of catechins is unavoidable to
36some extent. In this sense, ethyl lactate has demonstrated higher selectivity and
37efficiency with respect to commercial and other agrochemical solvents currently used to
38that end. Additionally, combining ethyl lactate with Supercritical CO₂ Anti-Solvent
39technique, a decaffeinated green tea precipitate could be obtained, overcoming
40limitations of presently studied procedures to obtain decaffeinated extracts and
41demonstrating to be a selective and effective alternative for catechins purification.

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43**Keywords:** Ethyl lactate; Green tea; Caffeine; Catechins; Decaffeination

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45 Summary

- 46 **1. Introduction**
- 47 **2. Green tea composition and bioactive compounds**
- 48 **3. Ethyl lactate: a novel and selective solvent for the removal of caffeine from**
- 49 **vegetal matrices**
- 50 **4. Green tea leaves decaffeination: traditional versus novel technologies**
- 51 **5. Recovery of caffeine and catechins**
- 52 **6. Conclusions**

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541. Introduction

55The growing environmental problems and the increasing scientific evidences related to
56the adverse health effects of certain chemical compounds frequently used in the
57industrial production have influenced in the demand of efficient production processes,
58more environmentally sustainable and safe. These issues led to develop the Green
59Chemistry concept. Green chemistry is the design of chemical products and processes
60that reduce or eliminate the use and generation of hazardous substances (Anastas &
61Kirchhoff, 2002), involving the term hazardous physical, toxicological and
62environmental considerations. On this point, Anastas and Warner (1998) introduced the
63twelve principles of Green Chemistry, a guiding framework for the greener design and
64implementation of benign new chemical products and processes. Some of the
65approaches considered in the twelve principles are the use of renewable feedstocks and
66energy sources, the reduction or elimination of waste and hazardous substances, the
67implementation of more energy-efficient processes and the use of green solvents.
68Regarding green solvents, it is important not only to use non-toxic and safe solvents, but
69also to use environmental friendly solvents and solvents which production follows the
70principles of Green Chemistry. The design and implementation of green solvents has
71been one of the most active areas of green chemistry over the past two decades.

72Ethyl lactate is an agrochemical solvent defined as GRAS (Generally Recognized as
73Safe) and due to its low toxicity it has been approved by FDA (Food and Drug
74Administration) and EFSA (European Food Safety Authority) as a pharmaceutical
75ingredient and food additive. Ethyl lactate has interesting properties, such as being a
76non-corrosive, non-carcinogenic, non-teratogenic, biodegradable and non-ozone
77depleting solvent.

78Ethyl lactate has demonstrated to be a more selective solvent for the extraction of
79caffeine from green tea leaves than water and organic solvents studied and used at
80industrial scale until now (Villanueva Bermejo, Mendiola, Ibáñez, Reglero & Fornari,
812015a). Added to CO₂ as a cosolvent and using the same conditions as commercially,
82higher caffeine extraction rate in a shorter extraction time period was also achieved
83(Villanueva Bermejo, Ibáñez, Reglero & Fornari, 2016a). Additionally, using this green
84solvent, a dry decaffeinated extract with high concentration of catechins and phenolic
85compounds that can be used as food ingredient or nutraceutical, can efficiently be
86obtained (Villanueva Bermejo et al., 2015b). Therefore, the drawbacks of the other

87methods recently or traditionally studied for this purpose, such as liquid-liquid
88partitioning, membrane technology or the use of adsorbents, can be solved.

89In this review, the different methods and solvents reported in the literature for the
90decaffeination and recovery of high valued catechins are revised. In this regard, Section
912 describes in detail the bioactive compounds present in green tea leaves, emphasizing
92the relevance of caffeine and catechins due to their bioactive properties and high content
93in this matrix. Section 3 describes the main characteristics of the green solvent ethyl
94lactate and delves into the use of this solvent that has been reported for food
95applications until now. The following two sections are focused on the extraction
96methods and solvents currently performed for obtaining caffeine and catechins from
97green tea, contrasting the results with that reported for ethyl lactate. On one hand,
98Section 4 inspects the most recent works related to decaffeination of tea leaves. On the
99other hand, Section 5 shows the latest studies to recover caffeine and catechins by
100applying new and traditional extraction and purification technologies. Finally, general
101remarks regarding the use of ethyl lactate as a new green solvent for the decaffeination
102of green tea leaves and green tea extracts are pointed out.

103In this review, the different methods and solvents described in the literature to green tea
104decaffeination and recovery of high valued catechins are revised. Particular attention is
105given to ethyl lactate, an agrochemical green solvent, which demonstrated high
106selectivity in the processing of green tea biomolecules.

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1082. Green tea composition and bioactive compounds

109Tea is the beverage prepared from the leaves and shoots of *Camellia sinensis* plants
110which belong to *Theaceae* family, the major varieties being the *sinensis* (*C. sinensis* var.
111*sinensis*) and the *assamica* (*C. sinensis* var. *assamica*). The brew prepared from the plant
112is one of the most consumed beverages in the world, mainly owing to its organoleptic
113properties and stimulant effects and in recent years has been intensely studied due to its
114potential health benefits. It has resulted in an increase in tea consumption in Europe and
115United States over the last 20 years (Engelhardt, 2010). Today tea is consumed, not only
116as beverage, but also as an ingredient to elaborate other food products, such as canned
117drinks, confectionery products, ice creams and cosmetic and phytotherapy products
118(Kawakatsu, Kobayashi, Sano & Nakajima, 1995; Shi & Schlegel, 2012). Variations of
119the processing result in the different types of teas (green, black, white, oolong and so
120on.) specially the so-called fermentation that is in fact an enzyme conversion of some

121constituents (mainly flavonols) by leaf enzymes. In the case of green tea it has
122undergone minimal oxidation during processing. For this reason, its composition and
123organoleptic properties differ from the other types of tea (Wan, Li & Zhang, 2009).
124Unlike fermented teas, green tea is a plentiful source of phenolic compounds which can
125reach up to 30 % (dry weight) of the leaves (Shahidi & Naczk, 2004; Shi & Schlegel,
1262012). Regarding phenolic compounds, flavonols and flavones (mainly in the form of
127flavonol and flavone glycosides, such as kaempferol, myricetin, quercetin, apigenin and
128luteolin glycosides), are present in the tea leaves, as well as phenolic acids such as 5-O-
129galloylquinic. These compounds are preserved during oxidation so that its concentration
130can be similar to that in other types of tea whereas the concentration of other phenolic
131compounds considerably changes. This is the case of catechins monomers, the major
132phenolic compounds contained in green tea leaves (Engelhardt, 2010).

133Catechins (flavan-3-ols) are the most abundant phenolic compounds in tea leaves (7-25
134% dry weight) and in some cases, they could represent 90 % of the phenolic compounds
135total mass (Shahidi & Naczk, 2004; Wei et al., 2011). Over the oxidation step catechins
136polymerization and oxidation is produced, therefore green tea contains greater amounts
137of these compounds than teas subjected to oxidation. Catechins contribute to
138astringency and bitterness and they are one of the most bioactive compounds of tea
139leaves (Chaturvedula & Prakash, 2011). In terms of stereochemistry of the 3',4'-
140dihydroxyphenyl group and hydroxyl at position 3 of the C-ring, catechins are divided
141in trans-catechins and cis-epicatechins. At the same time each of them can be present as
142two optical isomers, (+) and (-)-catechins / (+) and (-)-epicatechins, respectively.
143Catechins can be esterified with a gallic acid molecule at position 3 of the C-ring giving
144rise to catechin gallates. The main catechins forms (see Figure 1a) in green tea are (-)-
145epicatechin (EC), (-)-epigallocatechin (EGC), (-)-epicatechin gallate (ECG), and (-)-
146epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG). Of them, EGCG is usually the main catechin,
147followed by EGC and ECG, although it considerably varies in function of the
148geographical origin, cultivar and specie of tea shrub (Persson, 2013; Shahidi & Naczk,
1492004). Catechins are receiving considerable interest for their potential benefits on
150human health, such as antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antibiotic and antiviral
151effects (Bansal, Syan, Mathur & Choudhary, 2012; Osterburg, Gardner, Hyon, Neely &
152Babcock, 2009; Song, Lee & Seong, 2005). Additionally, they seem to exert a
153preventive effect against cardiovascular and some neurological diseases, type 2 diabetes

154and obesity (Khan & Mukhtar, 2007; Mika, Kostogrys, Franczyk-Żarów, Wikiera &
155Maślak, 2015).

156Other bioactive compounds contained in green tea leaves are alkaloids. Caffeine (Figure
1571b) is the most abundant (2-5 % dry weight). Other two alkaloids also present are
158theobromine and theophylline but its amount in green tea is lower than 0.4 % (dry
159weight) (Engelhardt, 2010). Caffeine is the most consumed alkaloid worldwide and its
160effects as stimulant of the central nervous system are well known. On one hand, health
161benefits derived from its consumption have been described, such as the increase in
162endurance and the ability to concentrate, the ability to focus attention and working
163short-term memory (Glade, 2010; Peeling & Dawson, 2007). Caffeine can act as
164analgesic combined with ergotamine and acetylsalicylic acid (Kumar & Ravishankar,
1652009) and has a positive effect against asthma (Debry, 1994). Likewise, caffeine has
166shown antioxidant properties (Kronschläger et al., 2013; Paston & Tarasov, 2011). On
167the other hand, caffeine can also cause adverse effects, such as high blood pressure,
168anxiety, sleep deprivation, tachycardia, abortion and miscarriages (Giannellia, Doyle,
169Roman, Pelerin & Hermon, 2003; Nehlig, Daval & Debry, 1992). Additionally, the
170acute intake of caffeine has been associated with high blood cholesterol, coronary
171diseases and a negative effect on glucose tolerance and insulin sensitivity (Farah, 2012).
172The adverse effects of caffeine on health motivated the production of decaffeinated
173products which possess a great commercial significance at present. Caffeine extracted
174after decaffeination process has commercial interest in different sectors, such as food,
175cosmetic and pharmaceutic industry (Kumar & Ravishankar, 2009).

176At present, commercial decaffeination is carried out using both liquid solvents and
177supercritical carbon dioxide. The various decaffeination processes in use can be divided
178in several categories. In all of them, it is common the moistening of the material by
179steaming and soaking in warm water to improve the transfer of caffeine to the solvent. It
180is due to swelling improves the diffusion and water destabilizes the caffeine complexes
181so caffeine is more available. The first commercial process was the direct solvent
182decaffeination. In this process, caffeine is extracted by an organic solvent which comes
183into direct contact with the plant material. Chlorinated solvents, such as
184dichloromethane, have traditionally been used but the use of these solvents has
185decreased due to their high toxicity and associated environmental problems (Wang et
186al., 2009). A number of other organic solvents have been proposed, though ethyl acetate
187is the most used in commercial practice (Vuong & Roach, 2014). Another process is the

188 indirect solvent decaffeination, in which water is used to remove the caffeine from the
189 plant material and then the caffeine-rich water extract is contacted countercurrently with
190 an organic solvent (generally is the same as described in the direct process) which
191 removes the caffeine from the water current. Finally, the water is then recycled to the
192 percolation battery to extract further caffeine (Clarke, 2003; Farah, de Paulis, Moreira,
193 Trugo & Martin, 2006). The third process with liquid solvents is the Swiss Water
194 Process. In this case the decaffeination is carried out only with water without the use of
195 organic solvents. Finally, the most recent process for the decaffeination consists in the
196 application of supercritical carbon dioxide (SCCO₂) (Ramalakshmi & Raghavan, 1999).
197 This process was patented for the first time by Zosel for the decaffeination of green
198 coffee beans (Zosel, 1974). As with organic solvents, it is necessary to bring the green
199 coffee beans before decaffeination to a moisture content of 30-50 % and/or to saturate
200 the SCCO₂ with water before coming into contact with the plant (Lack, Gamse & Marr,
201 2001). Although this process is more complex than the performed with liquid solvents,
202 the green properties of SCCO₂ make it more accepted by consumers and due to the high
203 selectivity for caffeine of this solvent, it is claimed that decaffeinated material produced
204 by this method has a better sensorial quality.

205 Despite the different procedures and solvents studied relative to the extraction of
206 caffeine from green tea, the loss of bioactive compounds (especially catechins) is
207 unavoidable to some extent (Henning et al., 2003). Thus, a selective extraction of
208 caffeine is desirable in the manufacturing of healthy green tea-derived products. In this
209 sense, many studies have been performed in relation to the extraction of caffeine and
210 catechins from green tea leaves and its subsequent fractionation. Overall, the reported
211 studies can be divided into two groups: studies related to the production of
212 decaffeinated green tea leaves (Section 3) and studies related to the recovery of caffeine
213 and catechins (Section 4).

214

215 **3. Ethyl lactate: a novel and selective solvent for the removal of caffeine from** 216 **vegetal matrices**

217 The green solvent ethyl lactate (Ethyl 2-hydroxypropanoate) (Figure 2) has recently
218 been thoroughly studied as an extraction solvent due to its interesting properties. Ethyl
219 lactate is naturally present in low quantities in some foods, such as certain fruits, meat,
220 soy and some fermented beverages, such as beer and wine. This organic solvent has
221 high solvent power since it can cover a wide range of polarities being soluble both in

222water and paraffin. Ethyl lactate is a viable alternative to traditional liquid solvents since
223it is an agrochemical solvent, fully biodegradable, non-corrosive, non-carcinogenic,
224non-teratogenic and non-ozone depleting. It is considered as GRAS (generally
225recognized as safe) and due to its low toxicity, was approved by the U.S. Food and Drug
226Administration (FDA) and European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) as pharmaceutical
227and food additive. Owing to its agrochemical character and the properties mentioned
228before, many processes have been studied with the aim of reducing the production costs
229and promoting its use as an alternative to harmful solvents currently used.

230In relation to its production, ethyl lactate can be produced industrially from
231petrochemical stocks, but it is mainly produced in biorefineries from processing of
232carbohydrate feedstocks, such as wastes from corn or sugar crops. Ethyl lactate is
233principally produced by esterification of lactic acid and ethanol with water as by-
234product. Nevertheless, this solvent is also produced from ammonium lactate instead of
235lactic acid when the fermentation is carried out in the presence of ammonia (Kwak,
236Hwang, Hwang & Chang, 2012) and it can be produced by using lactide (a cyclic dimer
237of lactic acid) and polylactide, but such process is not economically viable since this
238starting material is more expensive than the final product so that ethyl lactate itself is
239used to produce lactide and polylactides (Salerno & Domingo, 2014).

240Esterification is a self-catalyzed reaction, which is thermodynamically limited. For this
241reason the use of catalysts is necessary. Homogeneous mineral acids, such as sulfuric
242acid and phosphoric acid, have traditionally been used to carry out the esterification.
243Nevertheless, its use presents drawbacks, such as the corrosion of equipment, difficulties
244to recover the catalyst or the production of corrosive liquid waste. Heterogeneous acid
245catalysts (for example, ion-exchange resins, heteropolyacids and acid-treated clays,
246among others) represent an alternative to the mentioned shortcomings (Pereira, Silva &
247Rodrigues, 2011). Several authors have performed kinetic studies on the esterification of
248lactic acid with ethanol using different heterogeneous catalysts, at different conditions
249(temperatures, lactic acid/ethanol ratios and concentrations of aqueous lactic acid)
250(Delgado, Sanz & Beltrán, 2007; Pereira, Pinho, Silva & Rodrigues, 2008; Zhang, Ma
251& Yang, 2004). The conventional esterification, in which ethyl lactate is produced until
252equilibrium is reached and ethyl lactate is purified by distillation or other methods,
253requires an excess of ethanol to achieve higher conversions and to overcome
254equilibrium limitations being the recovery of products formed at equilibrium technically
255complex. For this reason, several procedures consisting of combining the reaction step

256with the separation are being intensely studied. In the reaction-separation hybrid
257processes, at least one of the products is continuously removed from the reaction
258medium shifting the equilibrium to products formation.

259One of the extraction-reaction processes is based on the use of membranes. In this
260respect, vapor permeation and pervaporation process have been studied for the ethyl
261lactate production and different membranes and layouts have been performed (Budd,
262Ricardo, Jafar, Stephenson & Hughes, 2004; Jafar, Budd & Hughes, 2002; Pereira,
263Silva, Pinho & Rodrigues, 2010).

264Another process studied consists in the reactive distillation, based on the use of a
265reactive distillation column in which the esterification reactor is integrated in the
266distillation column (Asthana, Kolah, Vu, Lira & Miller, 2005; Gao, Zhao, Zhou &
267Huang, 2007).

268A novel simultaneous extraction and reaction process for the production of ethyl lactate
269is based on using a simulated moving bed reactor (Pereira, Zabka, Silva & Rodrigues,
2702009), a type of continuous chromatographic reactor, and a simulated moving bed
271membrane reactor (Silva, Pereira & Rodrigues, 2010), which led to a reduction in the
272consumption of ethanol with respect to not using a set of membranes in each column.

273Another process is the catalytic extractive reaction. This process involves the
274partitioning of the reactants into a biphasic solvent system composed by a reactive polar
275liquid phase that contains the reactants and catalyst and an immiscible extractive
276organic solvent that is selective for the ethyl lactate, such as toluene, benzene or diethyl
277ether (Wicki & Nielsen, 2005).

278The production of ethyl lactate has also been studied through the enzymatic
279esterification of lactic acid with ethanol using conventional organic solvents (hexane
280and toluene) as well as ionic liquids as a reaction medium, taking advantage of the
281enantioselectivity, regioselectivity and chemoselectivity of enzymes such as lipase B
282from *Candida antarctica* to produce enantiomerically pure ethyl lactate (Findrik,
283Németh, Gubicza, Bélafi-Bakó & Vasic-Racki, 2012; Major, Németh, Bélafi-Bakó &
284Gubicza, 2010).

285Nowadays, the intensive research about the production of ethyl lactate has occasioned
286this solvent is being produced at even lower prices. This event, together with its
287physical, chemical and environmental benign properties has increased the attention to
288the use of ethyl lactate as a green solvent for many industrial applications, replacing

289traditional toxic halogenated and petroleum based solvents whose selling prices have
290increased.

291Regarding the industrial applications of ethyl lactate, it is used in food industry as an
292additive as well as in perfumery, but its main application is as solvent. Industrially, ethyl
293lactate is used in the coating industry increasing the performance of different materials,
294such as wood, polystyrene and metals and is used in paint manufacturing (Pereira et al.,
2952011). This solvent is also used in phytosanitary industry dissolving compounds with
296pesticide and herbicide activity. On account of its low boiling point, low vapor pressure,
297low surface tension and high solvency power, ethyl lactate is employed as cleaner
298solvent for polyurethane industry, electronic and precision parts, a variety of metal and
299other surfaces, due to its ability to remove oils, paint and adhesives, among others
300(Henneberry, Snively, Vasek & Datta, 2004). Consequently, ethyl lactate has industrially
301replaced non green solvents such as toluene, acetone or xylene (Nikles, Piao, Lane &
302Nikles, 2001). Regarding pharmaceutical and cosmetic industry, ethyl lactate can be
303used as excipient in order to improve the solubility of different bioactive compounds,
304for instance, antivirals and antibiotics or can be used in veterinary anthelmintic
305formulations (Greff, 2000). Additionally, ethyl lactate possess an emollient effect on
306skin and can act as topical penetration enhancing agent assisting the delivery of
307cosmetic and pharmaceutical agents into deep skin layers (Gupta, 2006). For this
308reason, ethyl lactate can be involved in different formulations, such as creams, powders,
309masks, lotions or serums. Further, ethyl lactate exhibits synergistic anti-acne properties
310itself and combined with salicylic acid (Wee, Kim & Ryu, 2006) and may increase the
311protection time against *Aedes aegypti* in repellent formulations (Drapeau et al., 2009).
312Besides, ethyl lactate has been studied for the treatment of contaminated soils. The
313amendment of the chelating agent ethylenediaminedisuccinic acid (EDDS) with ethyl
314lactate improved the efficiency for the removal of copper and polycyclic aromatic
315hydrocarbons from these soils (Guo et al., 2010; Yap, Gan & Ng, 2015). As regards to
316other uses of ethyl lactate reported in the literature, this green solvent has also been
317studied as a reaction medium for chemical synthesis (Wan, Cao & Jing, 2014) and also
318for chemical analysis as mobile phase modifier in liquid chromatography (Judge & Aab,
3192013) or as a buffer gas modifier in ion mobility spectrometry (Fernández-Maestre,
320Velasco & Hill, 2014).

321Despite ethyl lactate is used increasingly in industry and the research concerning its
322applications in different areas is growing, the information about its use as an extraction

323solvent of bioactive compounds from food is recent and scarce. Table 1 shows the food
324matrices and compounds studied until now using ethyl lactate as a solvent.

325The first works were focused on obtaining lipid compounds. Tombokan et al. (2008)
326studied the phase behavior of the ternary system sclareol – ethyl lactate – CO₂ with the
327aim of achieving a rich sclareol fraction by means of determining the best operation
328conditions for the design of extraction processes of such compound using ethyl lactate
329and the following antisolvent precipitation of the obtained solution by using CO₂ as
330antisolvent at pressures from 1.4 to 13.8 MPa and 35 °C. Authors concluded the
331solubility of sclareol in ethyl lactate decreased (higher amount of the compound
332recovered) as CO₂ was added at an amount higher than 30 % (mass %) and the pressure
333increased above 4.1 MPa. Nevertheless, the main studied compounds have been the
334carotenoids. In this sense, Ishida and Chapman (2009) studied the extraction of β-
335carotene, lutein and lycopene from carrots, white corn and tomatoes, respectively, using
336ethyl lactate and the results were compared with those obtained using ethanol, ethyl
337acetate and the mixture dichloromethane/methanol/water (40/40/20). The highest lutein
338and β-carotene extraction yield was obtained with ethanol. Even though the largest
339amount of lycopene was extracted with the mixture, using ethyl lactate similar amounts
340of lycopene were achieved. Similarly, with ethyl lactate the recovery of β-carotene and
341lutein was between 75-79 % and 65 % for cis-lycopene of that obtained with the
342mixture whose toxicity makes it not suitable for the use in food industry. In the case of
343ethyl acetate, a commonly studied solvent for carotenoids extraction, it was less
344effective than ethyl lactate. Strati and Oreopoulou (2011) studied the extraction of
345carotenoids from tomato processing wastes (peel and seeds) using ethyl lactate and
346comparing it with other organic solvents (hexane, acetone, ethanol and ethyl acetate). At
347room temperature and after 30 min, the concentration of lycopene in the ethyl lactate
348extracts was considerably higher than with the other solvents. With respect to the
349extraction yield in the range of 25 °C and 70 °C, the largest values were obtained with
350ethyl lactate, followed by acetone (14-21 % lower than the maximum achieved with
351ethyl lactate). Wu et al. (2011) developed a method to extract astaxanthin from
352*Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous*. A treatment with an organic acid to break down the
353cell wall followed by a solvent extraction was performed. The solvents studied were
354petroleum ether, acetone, ethanol, hexane and ethyl lactate being the latter the solvent
355with which the best results were obtained. Authors optimized the extraction time using
356ethyl lactate and different mixtures with ethanol at ambient temperature. Using lactic

357acid in the cell wall break down step and the mixture ethyl lactate/ethanol (1/1) in the
358extraction step, very similar results to the obtained using DMSO (first step) and acetone
359(extraction solvent) were achieved, with the additional benefit of being a green
360procedure. On the other hand, Hernández et al. (2011) and Vicente (2011) reported the
361fractionation of edible oil compounds with ethyl lactate, with the objective of being
362exploited in the recovery of tocopherol and squalene from olive oil deodorizer
363distillates, due to the mixtures of ethyl lactate with lipid type substances usually present
364partial liquid-liquid miscibility with upper critical solution temperature critical point.
365Hernández et al. (2011) studied the liquid-liquid phase transition from squalene +
366triglyceride mixtures (30 % mass squalene, simulating the composition of the
367deodorizer distillates) at 25 °C and 40 °C and ambient pressure. At both conditions and
368for mixtures with 90 % and 80 % (wt %) ethyl lactate, a selective extraction of squalene
369was accomplished, especially at 25 °C (42 % squalene free of solvent in ethyl lactate
370rich phase). This means a 1.4 fold increase of squalene with respect to the initial
371composition and a separation factor (expressed as squalene and triglycerides partition
372coefficients ratio) higher than 3 at 25 °C. Then, a selective recovery of squalene could
373be feasible from these mixtures at low temperature and using low amount of ethyl
374lactate. Vicente et al. (2011) studied de liquid-liquid equilibrium of the ternary mixture
375ethyl lactate – olive oil – α -tocopherol at 15 °C and 25 °C, determining as Hernández et
376al. (2011) that low temperatures are appropriate for the extraction of this compound
377from olive oil using ethyl lactate (partition coefficient around 1 at 25 °C and higher than
3781.3 at 15 °C as well as a separation factor between α -tocopherol and olive oil higher at
379lower temperature). Considering this data, authors suggested a two-step extraction
380process for obtaining α -tocopherol. From a 27 % (wt %) of α -tocopherol in the raw
381material (olive oil – α -tocopherol) and contacting with sufficient ethyl lactate, two
382phases (oil and ethyl lactate-rich phase) were formed in both steps, achieving an α -
383tocopherol extraction yield (expressed as mass of α -tocopherol in ethyl lactate / mass of
384 α -tocopherol in raw material) of 85 % after the two steps. Both yield and separation
385factors indicated good selectivity of ethyl lactate. Unlike the others, Golmakani et al.
386(2012) evaluated the use of pressurized ethyl lactate combined with ethanol for the
387extraction of γ -linolenic acid from *Arthrospira platensis* (Spirulina microalgae). In this
388case, different experimental temperatures (from 60 to 180 °C), pressures (from 3.4 to
38920.7 MPa), time (from 5 to 15 min) and solvent compositions (from 100 % ethyl lactate

390to 100 % ethanol) were tested. At 180 °C, 20.7 MPa, 15 min with the mixture ethyl
391lactate + ethanol (50:50 v/v) authors reached 64 % recovery of γ -linolenic acid.
392Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2014) reported the ability of different green solvents for the
393extraction of thymol and essential oil from several thyme plants. Authors studied the
394extraction by PLE (Pressurized Liquid Extraction) comparing ethanol, limonene and
395ethyl lactate as solvents, and besides the SFE (Supercritical Fluid Extraction) with pure
396CO₂ as well as using these three organic solvents as CO₂ co-solvents. Regarding PLE,
397the highest concentration in the extract of thymol was obtained with limonene followed
398by ethyl lactate. Nevertheless, using the three solvents similar recoveries were achieved
399which is greater than the reported in the literature by using subcritical water extraction
400and the non-green solvent hexane, as well as by conventional methods such as steam
401distillation and soxhlet extraction (Dawidowicz, Rado, Wianowska, Mardarowicz &
402Gawdzik, 2008; Dawidowicz, Rado & Wianowska, 2009). Regarding SFE extractions,
403there was not any improvement with respect to pure CO₂ on thymol extraction when the
404three co-solvents were assessed and therefore, similar recoveries of thymol were
405attained.

406Unlike aforementioned studies, Lores et al. (2015) assayed the feasible use of ethyl
407lactate as extraction solvent of various phenolic compounds from common broom
408(*Cytisus scoparius*). To that end, several PLE extractions at 120 °C with methanol/water
409and ethyl lactate/water mixtures (50 % v/v) were carried out. With both mixtures, high
410phenolic compounds concentration, extracts with similar polyphenols composition
411profile and similar overall phenolic compounds concentration and antioxidant activities
412were obtained. Authors concluded ethyl lactate could be used to replace the toxic
413solvent methanol, which have already been studied for the extraction of phenolic
414compound from other species of the genus *Cytisus*.

415Caffeine is another food compound whose extraction performance with ethyl lactate has
416been determined. Manic et al. (2012) measured the solubility of caffeine in ethyl lactate
417at ambient pressure and temperatures from 23 °C to 60 °C. This solubility is very similar
418to that in water and higher than in other organic solvents thoroughly studied for the
419extraction of this alkaloid, such as ethyl acetate, ethanol, acetone and methanol
420(Shalmashi & Golmohammad, 2010). In addition, authors observed a feasible co-
421solvent effect when ethyl lactate contained a small amount of water due to a
422considerable increase in the solubility of this alkaloid was observed. This co-solvent
423effect was recently studied by Villanueva Bermejo, Reglero, Stateva and Fornari

424(2016b). In that work, the solubility of caffeine and ferulic acid in different ethyl lactate
425+ water mixtures was measured at ambient temperature and pressure and it was
426demonstrated for both compounds that the solubility in the respective mixed solvents
427was considerably higher than in either pure ethyl lactate or water. On the basis of this,
428Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2016a; 2015a; 2013a) carried out a series of studies to
429estimate the selectivity of ethyl lactate for the extraction of caffeine from green coffee
430beans and green tea leaves and concluding it could be used in this way for the
431production of decaffeinated products. In addition to ethyl lactate and by way of
432comparison, authors also checked the selectivity of other solvents, such as water and
433ethyl acetate (two solvents used at industrial scale in the production of decaffeinated
434products) and ethanol. In the case of green coffee beans (Villanueva Bermejo et al.,
4352013a), authors studied the PLE of caffeine and total phenolic and lipid compounds
436comparing ethyl lactate, ethyl acetate and ethanol as extraction solvents. Although the
437highest concentration of caffeine in the extracts was obtained with ethyl acetate, ethyl
438lactate provided the highest caffeine recovery (around 60 % of the initial caffeine after
43910 min extraction time). Relative to selectivity, the caffeine/phenolic compounds ratio
440(expressed as the distribution coefficient ratio of both compounds) was very similar for
441the three solvents. However the caffeine/lipid compounds ratio obtained with ethyl
442lactate was much higher than the one obtained with ethyl acetate. In all cases the
443selectivity values were higher than 1, showing all these three solvents, a great selectivity
444for caffeine. In the case of green tea leaves, authors studied the PLE of caffeine and
445monomeric catechins comparing ethyl lactate, water and ethyl lactate + water mixtures
446(Villanueva Bermejo et al., 2015a) and the SFE of these compounds comparing ethyl
447lactate, ethyl acetate and ethanol as co-solventes for the CO₂ (Villanueva Bermejo et al.,
4482016a). Previously, authors defined the phase behavior of the ethyl lactate + CO₂ binary
449system (Villanueva Bermejo, Ibáñez, Stateva & Fornari, 2013b) measuring the
450solubility of CO₂ in the ethyl lactate-rich phase (38, 45 and 50 °C and pressures up to 8.1
451MPa) and from the solubility of ethyl lactate in the gas phase reported by Chylinski and
452Gregorowicz (1998). More recently, Paninho, Nunes, Paiva and Najdanovic-Visak
453(2013) reported the equilibrium compositions in a wider range of temperatures (40 °C-
454120 °C) and pressures (0.4-17 MPa). In other contribution, Villanueva Bermejo et al.
455(2015b) reported a method to produce decaffeinated green tea extracts with high
456catechins content by PLE using ethyl lactate followed by SAS (supercritical anti-
457solvent) precipitation with CO₂ obtaining extracts with less than 1 % mass of caffeine.

458A more detailed description in relation to the production of ethyl lactate, its physico-
459chemical properties and applications, can be found in the document reported by Fornari,
460Villanueva Bermejo and Reglero (2014).

461

4624. **Green tea leaves decaffeination: traditional versus novel technologies**

463In relation to the production of decaffeinated green tea leaves, Table 2 shows different
464studies on this point. Although different procedures have been examined, SCCO₂ has
465been the most studied solvent.

466Regarding the use of liquid solvent, Liang et al. (2007) studied a decaffeination process
467by water. Authors reached a selective caffeine removal when process was carried out
468with fresh green tea leaves. However, the recovery of catechins was high (49-68 mass
469%) when the process was performed with dry tea leaves in the same way as commercial
470process is carried out. Lou et al. (2012) studied the decaffeination process of green tea
471by means of two extraction stages: a pre-treatment by microwaves for 6 min followed
472by an extraction under vacuum with water at around 0 °C temperature. In this way, 87.6
473% recovery of caffeine, relative to the initial content in the leaves, was obtained.
474Regarding the co-extraction of other interesting compounds, authors reached 20.1 %
475and 36.2 % recovery of caffeine and phenolic compounds, respectively. Villanueva
476Bermejo et al. (2015a) studied the selectivity of ethyl lactate to extract caffeine from
477green tea leaves by PLE. The results were compared with the obtained with water,
478which is one of the solvents currently used for the commercial decaffeination of
479vegetable matrices. This study was performed on the basis of the results obtained by the
480authors in a previous work (Villanueva Bermejo et al., 2013a) in which the selectivity of
481pressurized ethyl lactate for the extraction of caffeine from green coffee beans was
482assessed comparing this with the obtained by using ethyl acetate (another solvent used
483at industrial scale for the decaffeination) and ethanol (another green solvent thoroughly
484studied for the extraction of caffeine). In that work (Villanueva Bermejo et al., 2013a),
485ethyl lactate demonstrated to be a selective solvent for the decaffeination of green coffee
486beans. Additionally, by using ethyl lactate instead of ethyl acetate and ethanol, the co-
487extraction of compounds responsible for the organoleptic and healthy properties of
488coffee, such as coffee oil and phenolic compounds, was preserved to a greater extent.
489For the decaffeination of green tea leaves and just as for the decaffeination of coffee
490beans, Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2015a) concluded that ethyl lactate was a more
491selective solvent for the extraction of caffeine preventing the co-extraction of catechins.

492By using ethyl lactate or ethyl lactate:water mixtures (50:50), caffeine/catechins ratios
493(expressed as the distribution coefficient ratio of both compounds) from 2.8 to 5.5 and
494caffeine recoveries up to 92 % were obtained after 20 min extraction time, whereas
495when pure water was used, the ratio was reduced by half.

496In regards to the use of supercritical fluids, Tang et al. (2010) carried out the extraction
497of caffeine by SCCO₂ using water as co-solvent and assisted by ultrasound. By means of
498this combined process, authors reached a caffeine recovery close to 79 %. In the
499majority of reported studies related to the use of SCCO₂ for the decaffeination of green
500tea leaves, the co-solvents used were water or ethanol, which were previously put in
501contact with the leaves moistening them before the extraction begins simulating in some
502way the commercial procedure. Park et al. (2007a) used ethanol as a co-solvent. At
503pressures from 23 MPa to 30 MPa and temperatures from 60 °C and 70 °C authors
504obtained caffeine recoveries about 93-97 %. However, a high amount of other
505compounds, such as catechins (recoveries between 41-68 %) and chlorophyll (around 43
506%) was co-extracted. In another contribution, Park et al. (2007b) used water as a co-
507solvent. In this case, the caffeine recovery was only 77 % and catechins recovery (close
508to 75 %) was higher than with ethanol at the same pressure and temperature conditions
509but using twice the amount of co-solvent. Kim et al. (2008) also studied the
510decaffeination of green tea leaves moistened with water as a co-solvent. The largest
511caffeine/EGCG ratio obtained was 2.6, although the recovery of caffeine achieved was
512low (54 %). When extraction temperature raised an increase in the extraction of
513caffeine, but a considerable reduction of the caffeine/EGCG ratio, was also observed.

514On the other hand, Sun et al. (2010) used water, ethanol and both their mixtures as co-
515solvents, but in this case the tea leaves were not moistened and the co-solvent was
516previously pumped and mixed with the CO₂. The best results were achieved with
517ethanol reaching a caffeine recovery close to 70.2 % and 11.3 caffeine/catechins ratio.
518Huang et al. (2007) carried out the supercritical extraction both moistening the leaves
519and soaking previously the raw material followed by pumping the mixture CO₂-co-
520solvent in a continuous mode. According to the results obtained, a better
521caffeine/catechins ratio was reached when the vegetable material was just moistened
522and the co-solvent was not continuously added to CO₂. Finally, Villanueva Bermejo et
523al. (2016a) studied the extraction of caffeine and monomeric catechins comparing ethyl
524lactate, ethyl acetate and ethanol as a co-solvents for the SCCO₂. Two extraction modes
525were tested: a static mode, in which green tea leaves were soaked with the co-solvent

526 and loaded into the extraction cell and a dynamic mode, in which dry leaves were
527 loaded into the extraction cell and then CO₂ and co-solvent were continuously pumped
528 and mixed before being entered in the cell. The highest amount of caffeine was obtained
529 with ethyl lactate regardless of the extraction mode employed, followed by ethanol
530 (amount 17-38 % lower), whereas the yield obtained with ethyl acetate (49-71 % lower)
531 was similar to the obtained with pure CO₂. In all cases, the co-extraction of catechins
532 was lower than 2 % (mass %). Furthermore, the greatest caffeine extraction rates at the
533 early extraction stages (after 14 min) were achieved with ethyl lactate as co-solvent. The
534 results corresponding to the static extraction curves were adjusted using the Sovová
535 model. In this case, mass transfer coefficient in the fluid phase with ethyl lactate was 1.4
536 and 2.6 times higher than with ethanol and ethyl acetate, respectively. As a
537 consequence, ethyl lactate proved to be the most efficient co-solvent for the
538 supercritical decaffeination of green tea leaves.

539 In conclusion, by using SCCO₂ together with ethanol or water as co-solvents a high
540 caffeine extraction rate can be achieved, although an appreciable extraction of catechins
541 is also produced. Ethyl lactate has proved to be a better co-solvent than ethanol for the
542 extraction of caffeine from green tea leaves. Industrially, water is the solvent employed
543 together with SCCO₂. On the other hand, the use of water instead of green organic
544 solvents can reduce processing costs. Considering the work reported by Park et al.
545 (2007b) using water as co-solvent (in a similar way as the industrial process), the
546 recovery of caffeine reached (42 %) was very similar to that obtained using ethyl lactate
547 (38 %) at the same extraction conditions (30 MPa, 70 °C, 120 min, static mode). To this
548 should be considered that the percentage of water added to CO₂ (5.8 %) and the
549 CO₂/green tea ratio (102 g/g) employed by Park et al. (2007b) was much higher than the
550 amounts applied by Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2016a) after 120 min when used ethyl
551 lactate (2.2 % and 26 g/g, respectively). Therefore, the green solvent ethyl lactate could
552 be a new alternative used as a co-solvent for the decaffeination of green tea leaves by
553 supercritical fluid extraction.

554

555. **Recovery of caffeine and catechins**

556 In this regard, the studies are focused on the production of caffeine and catechins-rich
557 extracts and the production of green tea extracts, concentrated in catechins but with low
558 content of caffeine.

559 Table 3 shows different studies related to the extraction of caffeine and catechins from
560 green tea leaves, in which different procedures, solvents and extraction conditions are
561 reported. The extracts were obtained using both traditional and new extraction methods,
562 such as ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) or microwave-assisted extraction (MAE).
563 Additionally, different extraction conditions and solvents were assessed being water and
564 water/ethanol mixtures the most used.

565 With respect to the conventional extraction technologies, Gadkari et al. (2014) tested
566 several solvents (ethyl acetate, diethyl ether, dichloromethane, chloroform and hexane)
567 reaching the highest amount of caffeine in the extracts using the chlorinated solvents,
568 but the greatest catechins concentration and antioxidant activity with ethyl acetate.
569 Zhang et al. (2014) and Kanda et al. (2013) studied solvents with lower toxicity than
570 chlorinated solvents. Zhang et al. (2014) evaluated the extraction of several catechins
571 using deep eutectic solvents (DES) in comparison with water and the organic solvents
572 methanol, acetonitrile, ethanol and hexane. The catechins extraction yields were higher
573 using DES. In this case, the most efficient DES was determined to be choline
574 chloride/ethylene glycol (1:5) mixture, especially when 30 % water was added to the
575 mixture. Kanda et al. (2013) reported the extraction of caffeine, catechins and water
576 using liquefied dimethyl ether. The material studied were green tea leaves with high
577 moisture content that have been previously subjected to water extraction. The objective
578 was to obtain an extract with high content of caffeine and the drying of the tea
579 byproduct. Authors determined around 35 % catechins recovery and reached a tea
580 byproduct with less than 9 % water and free of caffeine. Perva-Uzunalic et al. (2006)
581 studied several organic solvents (acetone, methanol, ethanol and acetonitrile) and
582 different organic solvent/water mixtures. The greatest caffeine and catechins recoveries
583 were achieved with acetone/water and acetonitrile/water mixtures, respectively.
584 Zimmermann and Gleichenhagen (2011) and Vuong et al. (2013a) studied various
585 extraction conditions employing water at different pH values. In both cases the highest
586 concentration and extraction yield for catechins was obtained at pH of less than 5 due to
587 the higher stability of flavanols at acid conditions. In the case of caffeine, pH
588 demonstrated to exert no effect on the extraction. Rusak et al. (2008) tested the
589 extraction of these compounds with water, water with lemon juice and aqueous ethanol
590 at different concentrations. In this case, the majority of catechins were obtained with
591 aqueous ethanol and no differences were observed when pH decreased as a consequence
592 of adding lemon juice compared to pure water.

593 Regarding new extraction technologies, Choung and Lee (2011) by means of UAE
594 achieved similar amounts of caffeine but amounts of catechins slightly lower than the
595 obtained after 24 hours extraction at room temperature using ethanol/water mixtures
596 with phosphoric acid. Nevertheless, the time needed to reach these values was
597 appreciably shorter by UAE. Subsequently, Choung et al (2014) were carried out the
598 same extractions with the same solvent without acid addition. After 30 min by UAE,
599 authors obtained amounts of catechins slightly higher than the obtained after 2 hours at
600 ambient temperature. Pan et al. (2003) explored water, ethanol, methanol, acetone and
601 their water mixtures as solvents as well as different extraction techniques (MAE, UAE
602 and conventional extraction technologies). The highest quantities of caffeine and
603 catechins were achieved by MAE with the mixture ethanol/water. Miyashita and Etoh
604 (2013) studied the extraction of these compounds using subcritical water (SWE) and
605 applying different pressure and temperature. In this case, similar extracts were obtained,
606 but when the highest pressure and temperature was applied the extraction time was the
607 shortest. On the contrary, Jun (2009) studied the effect of high pressures for the
608 extraction of caffeine. Acetone, methanol, ethanol and their water mixtures were tested.
609 The amounts of caffeine extracted were similar to that obtained with conventional
610 extraction methods, but applying high pressures these amounts were achieved after 1
611 min extraction only. In another contribution, Xi et al. (2014) determined the total
612 amount of phenolic compounds removed at the same extraction conditions reported in
613 the previous work. In this case, after 2 minutes much higher amounts of these
614 compounds were obtained comparing with the obtained at 85 °C and ambient pressure.
615 Taking into account all these results, the caffeine and catechins extraction yield was low
616 when pure organic solvents were employed whereas the yield considerably increased
617 when either aqueous mixtures or pure water, at high temperature, were used. Likewise,
618 applying new extraction technologies similar or even higher amounts of these
619 compounds were attained with short extraction times.

620 Table 4 shows different procedures related to the production of green tea extracts with
621 low content in caffeine reported in the literature. In most of these studies the starting
622 material consisted of aqueous extracts.

623 Regarding the use of liquid solvents, Row and Jin (2006) carried out the removal of
624 caffeine by two sequential extractions with chloroform and finally the catechins were
625 extracted from the aqueous phase with ethyl acetate. Choung et al. (2014) firstly carried
626 out a fractionation by means of three sequential extractions with ethyl acetate. After that

627more than 95 % of catechins from the starting extract were recovered. Then, the solvent
628was evaporated and the dry extract was dissolved into water and subjected to several
629sequential extractions with dichloromethane to remove the remaining caffeine. Finally,
63096.2 % of the initial amount of caffeine and only 1.2 % of catechins were removed with
631dichloromethane, demonstrating that chlorinated solvents have high selectivity for
632caffeine. Despite this, the use of chlorinated solvents has decreased due to their high
633toxicity and associated environmental problems. Dong et al. (2011a) studied three
634organic solvents (ethyl acetate, n-butanol and n-hexane) to isolate the catechins being
635ethyl acetate the most efficient solvent for that purpose. Then, caffeine was removed
636from the extract concentrated in catechins by sequential precipitation with a citric acid
637solution. In this case, the removal of caffeine reached was 78.8 % and therefore it was
638less efficient than chlorinated solvents. Alternatively, Vuong et al. (2013b) applied the
639selective extraction of caffeine reported by Liang et al. (2007) to subsequently obtain an
640aqueous extract rich in catechins and with low content in caffeine. Finally, the water
641was dried by spray drying or freeze-drying. Despite obtaining a dry extract with 0.73 %
642caffeine and 19.6 % catechins, a drawback of this procedure is that decaffeination step
643is carried out on the fresh green tea leaves to avoid the high loss of catechins.

644By contrast, Sosa et al. (2011) carried out the precipitation and encapsulation of
645polyphenols by SAS precipitation with SCCO₂ from a green tea extract obtained by
646MAE with acetone. Despite the main objective of the study was to obtain a high
647precipitation and encapsulation yield of polyphenols and catechins, the SAS
648precipitation allowed to obtain a partial fractionating of the tea extract as only 13 % of
649initial caffeine was encapsulated in the final product.

650On the other hand, Nwuha (2000) studied the performance of several nanofiltration
651membranes for the separation of caffeine and catechins from a commercial green tea
652extract. Authors measured the ability to retain or reject the compounds of interest.
653Several parameters were tested, such as the type of membrane, its stability, the flow
654effect and the solvent composition, achieving the best fractionation results with the G-
65510 and G-20 membranes and using 80 % ethanol.

656Monsanto et al. (2014) studied the separation of caffeine and catechins by using the tea
657creaming effect and the influence of three factors (precipitation agents, pH and
658temperature) to enhance the precipitation of catechins minimizing the precipitation of
659caffeine. The best results were reached when hydroxypropylmethylcellulose and
660polyvinylpyrrolidone were used as precipitation agents whereas pH was found not to be

661significant. Nevertheless, although the catechins/caffeine ratio in the precipitate
662increased, 40 % of caffeine contained in the aqueous extract also precipitated.

663Regarding the use of adsorbents, many materials have been studied to separate caffeine
664and catechins being the ethanol/water mixtures the most commonly used solvents to
665carry out the desorption steps. In general, these adsorbents provide a high selectivity for
666the separation of these compounds. In this sense, several studies have been carried out
667using lignocellulose from different woods. Sakanaka (2003) used cellulose and
668lignocellulose from cedar wood sawdust obtaining an EGCG/caffeine ratio of 264.6
669from a green tea extract with a ratio of 1.4. Ye et al. (2009) used lignocellulose from
670woody tea stalk, pine sawdust and sugarcane bagasse and they were compared with
671synthetic macroporous resin HPD 600. Tea stalk lignocellulose showed a better
672caffeine/catechins selectivity coefficient for the separation (catechins/caffeine ratio of
6733.35, whereas for HPD 600 resin it was 0.54). Eluting in two steps with ethanol/water
674mixtures an extract with a catechins/caffeine ratio of 152 could be obtained. In a
675following study, Ye et al. (2010) investigated the graft copolymerization of N-
676vinylpyrrolidone onto fir sawdust lignocellulose with the aim of improving the retention
677of catechins by lignocellulose. In this case, the adsorption capacity to catechins for the
678copolymerized lignocellulose after modification increased by 36–40%. Yet et al. (2007)
679also studied the application of active carbon to produce a decaffeinated green tea extract
680from partially decaffeinated green tea leaves. After 4 h of static contact, the caffeine
681content was reduced by 31 % and the loss of catechins was 16.2 % by using this
682adsorbent. In another work, Ye et al. (2011) used Polyamide-6 for the separation. Using
683this polyamide, a caffeine/catechins selectivity coefficient of 21.7 was obtained. After
684one adsorption-desorption cycle authors obtained an extract with a catechins/caffeine
685ratio of 366.9. Lu et al. (2010) used poly(acrylamide-co-ethylene glycol
686dimethylacrylate) as adsorbent. Starting with an initial catechins/caffeine ratio of 6.9 a
687final ratio of 430 was obtained after two elution steps with ethanol/water mixtures.
688Alternatively, Dong et al. (2011b) used polyvinylpolypyrrolidone (PVPP) as adsorbent.
689Authors studied the static desorption of caffeine and catechins by two elution stages, the
690first with water and the second with a DMSO/ethanol mixture. After that, a
691catechins/caffeine ratio of 203 from an initial ratio of 19.5 could be obtained. More
692recently, Fan et al. (2014) comprehensively studied the desorption process from PVPP.
693The more efficient solvents studied to that end were DMF (elution of 87.3 % of
694adsorbed catechins) and DMSO (94.2 %). Addition of relatively small amounts of

695 ethanol to these solvents enhanced the process efficiency. By using an ethanol/water
696 mixture for the first elution stage and DMSO/ethanol for the second stage an extract
697 with only 0.18 % of the total caffeine loaded was obtained.

698 Li et al. (2005) performed a process to fractionate caffeine and green tea polyphenols by
699 ultrafiltration with a cellulose acetate–titanium composite ultrafiltration membrane,
700 followed by adsorption with a polyamide resin. After ultrafiltration stage, an extract
701 with polyphenols content of more than 40 % (mass %) was obtained. After adsorption
702 on the resin and elution with a mixture composed by ethanol/ethyl acetate and acetone,
703 an extract containing more than 90 % polyphenols and less than 4 % (mass %) caffeine
704 was obtained.

705 Finally, Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2015b) reported a green method to produce a
706 solvent-free extract from green tea leaves with high content of catechins and low
707 content of caffeine, in two steps and using green solvents. The method combined the
708 PLE of green tea leaves using ethyl lactate with the selective precipitation of catechins
709 using the supercritical carbon dioxide-antisolvent technique (SAS). The SAS
710 precipitation of ethyl lactate produced precipitates with caffeine reductions higher than
711 90 % relative to the caffeine contained in the ethyl lactate extracts. By this combined
712 method, precipitates with less than 1 % mass of caffeine that could be considered
713 decaffeinated were obtained. Additionally, a catechins and phenolic compounds
714 enrichment was produced, obtaining precipitates with 23 % mass of catechins and high
715 content of phenolic compounds (550-580 mg GAE/g precipitate) which represents an
716 increase of up to 25% with respect to the phenolic compounds contained in the PLE
717 extracts.

718 The combined method PLE using ethyl lactate as solvent and SAS precipitation
719 provides some features which make it attractive in comparison with the aforementioned
720 procedures to fractionate caffeine and catechins from green tea extracts. Combined
721 method ethyl lactate extract and SAS is a procedure that uses only green solvents,
722 unlike the liquid-liquid partition by chlorinated solvents. This combined procedure is
723 also a very selective method to remove the caffeine from the extracts, unlike cream
724 formation. Membrane technology shows several technological shortcomings, such as
725 the flow rate decrease over time, or the necessity of a cleaning step which sometimes
726 requires using toxic solvents, such as strong mineral acids and bases. Adsorbents
727 present high selectivity, however for obtaining the results previously mentioned, a
728 certain amount of time to allow a good contact between compounds and adsorbent, as

729well as low flow rates during the elution stages were needed. Unlike them, during SAS
730step a faster mass transfer rate between the supercritical fluid and the liquid extract is
731produced so that it constitutes a less time-consuming method. Additionally all these
732methods require large volumes of solvent that have to be treated, whereas using the
733combined method PLE with ethyl lactate and SAS a solvent-free extract is produced.

734

7356. Conclusions

736The increasing of scientific evidences related to the adverse health effects of certain
737solvents commonly used, as well as the environmental regulations and social
738consciousness regarding ecological problems is promoting the development and
739appearance of new green solvents in the industry. Ethyl lactate is an agrochemical green
740solvent, non-corrosive, non-carcinogenic, non-teratogenic and non-ozone depleting
741recently studied for food processing. Several potential applications are related to the
742extraction of lipid related compounds, such as carotenoids, and the recovery of other
743high value bioactive substances from plants, such as caffeine from green coffee beans
744and green tea. Green tea and its decaffeinated products are foodstuffs which focus a
745great commercial attention due to its interesting healthy properties and beverages and
746food ingredients elaborated from it are one of the most consumed worldwide. In this
747sense, ethyl lactate either for solid-liquid extraction or as a co-solvent of SCCO_2 has
748proved to be a good solvent to be used for decaffeination improving the selectivity and
749efficiency with respect to commercial solvents currently used to that end, such as water
750and ethyl acetate or other agrochemical solvent, such as ethanol. In addition to it, green
751tea extracts obtained with ethyl lactate can be selectively fractionated by SAS
752precipitation obtaining a dry decaffeinated extract with high concentration of catechins
753and phenolic compounds. Different methods have been reported in the literature for this
754purpose, such as the use of membranes, adsorbents or solvent partitioning. Unlike SAS
755precipitation of a green tea extract obtained with ethyl lactate, the results obtained by
756these other methods were unsatisfactory due to low production yields, extracts with
757relatively high caffeine content or low catechins/caffeine ratio, as well as being time-
758consuming methods and require high amounts of solvents.

759Therefore, ethyl lactate is a potential alternative for the production of decaffeinated
760green tea leaves or decaffeinated ingredients from green tea that could be used as
761functional ingredients, replacing with more selectivity and efficiency other solvents and
762processes currently studied and/or used.

763

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1125 **Table 1.** Extraction studies of bioactive compounds reported in the literature using ethyl
 1126 lactate.

1127

Group	Compound	Food matrix	Reference
Lipid compounds	Sclareol	Clary sage	Tombokan, Aguda, Danehower, Kilpatrick and Carbonell (2008)
	β -carotene, lutein and lycopene	Carrots, white corn and tomatoes	Ishida and Chapman (2009)
	Lycopene	Tomato waste	Strati and Oreopoulou (2011)
	Astaxanthin	<i>Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous</i>	Wu, Lu and Yu (2011)
	Squalene and α -tocopherol	Olive oil deodorizer distillates	Hernández et al. (2011); Vicente, Paiva, Fornari and Najdanovic-Visak (2011)
	γ -linolenic acid	Spirulina microalgae	Golmakani, Mendiola, Rezaei and Ibáñez (2012)
	Thymol	Thyme plants	Villanueva et al. (2014)
Phenolic compounds		<i>Cytisus scoparius</i>	Lores, Pájaro, Álvarez-Casas, Domínguez and García-Jares (2015)
Alkaloids	Caffeine	Green coffee beans	Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2013a)
	Caffeine	Green tea leaves	Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2015a); Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2016a)
	Caffeine	Green tea extracts	Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2015b)

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1130**Table 2.** Studies related to the production of green tea leaves with low content in
1131caffeine.

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Extraction conditions	Solvent	Recovery	Reference
100 °C, 3 min, 20 m/m ^a (fresh tea leaves)	Water	Caffeine: 83 % Catechins: 5 %	Liang et al. (2007)
Stage 1: MAE, 6 min Stage 2: 0.1 MPa, 0 C, 150 min, 10 m/m	Water	Caffeine: 87.6 % Catechins: 20.1 %	Lou et al. (2012)
PLE: 10 MPa, 150 °C, 20 min	Ethyl lactate	Caffeine: 75.9 % Catechins: 36.3 %	Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2015a)
Ultrasonic-enhanced SFE: 30 MPa, 45 °C, 240 min, 40 % co-solvent previously added to tea, 2 m/m	SCCO ₂ -water	Caffeine: 78.4 %	Tang, Li, Lv and Jiang (2010)
SFE: 30 MPa, 70 °C, 120 min; 4.6 % co-solvent previously added to tea, 102 m/m	SCCO ₂ -water	Caffeine: 92.8 % Catechins: 68.0 %	Park et al. (2007a)
SFE: 30 MPa, 70 °C, 120 min; 8.8 % co-solvent previously added to tea, 102 m/m	SCCO ₂ -water	Caffeine: 77.4 % Catechins: 75.3 %	Park et al. (1007b)
SFE: 40 MPa, 40 °C, 300 min, 7 % co-solvent previously added to tea; 28.1 m/m	SCCO ₂ -water	Caffeine: 54 % EGCG: 21 %	Kim, Kim, Kim, Oh and Lee (2008)
SFE: 30 MPa, 80 °C, 120 min; 3.5 % co-solvent, previously pumped and mixed with CO ₂ , 18 m/m	SCCO ₂ -water	Caffeine: 70.2 % Catechins: 6.2 %	Sun et al. (2010)
SFE: 30 MPa, 80 °C, 450 min; 0.03 % co-solvent previously added to tea, 900 m/m	SCCO ₂ -water	Caffeine: 95.6 % Catechins: 19.8 %	Huang, Wu, Chiu, Lai and Chang (2007)
SFE: 30 MPa, 70 °C, 210 min; 2.2 % co-solvent previously added to tea, 45 m/m	SCCO ₂ -ethyl lactate	Caffeine: 48.3 % Catechins: 1 %	Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2016b)

1133^amass of solvent / mass of plant material

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1135 **Table 3.** Studies related to the production of extracts rich in caffeine and catechins from
1136 green tea leaves using liquid solvents.

1137

Extraction conditions	Solvent	Extraction yield	Reference
<i>Conventional extraction techniques</i>			
25 °C, 20 min, 20 (m/m) ^a	ethyl acetate	Catechins: 356.4 mg/g extract Caffeine: 121.8 mg/g extract	Gadkari, Kadimi and Balaraman (2014)
75 °C, 30 min, 62.5 (m/m)	choline chloride / ethylene glycol (1:5) + 30 % water	Catechin, ECG, EGCG: 3.6; 35.3 and 114.2 mg/g plant	Zhang, Tang and Row (2014)
0.51 MPa, 20 °C, 90 min, 19.5 (m/m)	liquefied dimethyl ether	Catechins: 5.0 mg/g extract Caffeine: 0.55 mg/g extract	Kanda, Li and Makino (2013)
Boiling point, 120 min, 20 (m/m)	acetone / water (25:75)	Catechins: 188.1 mg/g plant Caffeine: 27.2 mg/g plant	Perva-Uzunalic et al. (2006)
70 °C, 7 min, 100 (m/m)	water with citric acid (pH 3)	Catechins: 588.8 mg/mL extract	Zimmermann and Gleichenhagen (2011)
80 °C, 30 min, 20 (m/m)	water (pH 5)	Catechins: 88.8 mg/g plant Caffeine: 27.4 mg/g plant	Vuong, Golding, Stathopoulos and Roach (2013a)
80 °C, 30 min, 100 (m/m)	ethanol / water (40:60)	Catechins: 333.9 mg/g plant	Rusak, Komes, Likic, Horzic and Kovac (2008)
25 °C, 120 min, 200 (m/m)	ethanol / water (40:60) and 2 % phosphoric acid	Catechins: 131.3 mg/g plant Caffeine: 24.3 mg/g plant	Choung, and Lee (2011)
<i>New extraction techniques</i>			
UAE, 40 °C, 30 min, 10 (m/m)	ethanol / water (40:60)	Catechins: 90.2 mg/g plant Caffeine: 19.7 mg/g plant	Choung et al. (2014)
MAE, 90 °C, 4 min, 20 (m/m)	ethanol / water (50:50)	Caffeine: 40 mg/g plant	Pan, Niu and Liu (2003)
SWE: 3 MPa, 130 °C, 1 min, 50 (m/m)	water	Catechins: 3.1 mg /mL extract Caffeine: 0.36 mg/mL extract	Miyashita and Etoh (2013)
500 MPa, 25 °C, 1 min, 20 (m/m)	ethanol / water (50:50)	Caffeine: 41.5 mg/g plant	Jun (2009)
500 MPa, 25 °C, 4 min, 20 (m/m)	ethanol / water (50:50)	Catechins: 232 mg/g extract Caffeine: 40 mg/g extract	Xi, Yan and He (2014)

1138^amass of solvent / mass of plant material

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1140 **Table 4.** Studies related to the production of green tea extracts with low content in
 1141 caffeine and rich in catechins.

1142

Production method	Reference
<i>Liquid solvents</i>	
Stage 1: Extraction of caffeine by chloroform Stage 2: Purification of catechins from aqueous phase by ethyl acetate	Row and Jin (2006).
Stage 1: Extraction of catechins by ethyl acetate Stage 2: Evaporation of extract and dissolution in water Stage 3: Purification of catechins removing caffeine by methylene chloride	Choung et al. (2014)
Stage 1: Extraction of catechins by ethyl acetate Stage 2: Purification of catechins precipitating caffeine by citric acid solution	Dong, Ye, Lu, Zheng and Liang (2011a)
Stage 1: Decaffeination of green tea leaves: water, 100 °C, 4 min, 20 m/m ³ Stage 2: Extraction by water (2 extractions: 80 °C, 30 min each one, 12 m/m and 8 m/m, respectively) followed by spray-drying	Vuong, Golding, Nguyen and Roach (2013b)
<i>Supercritical Fluids</i>	
Stage 1: MAE with acetone as solvent Stage 2: SAS precipitation: 9 MPa, 15 °C, CO ₂ / extract ratio \approx 1	Sosa, Rodríguez-Rojo, Mattea, Cismondi and Cocero (2011)
<i>Membrane technology</i>	
Nanofiltration: G-10 and G-20 membranes, 5 MPa, 23 °C, ethanol / water (80:20)	Nwuha (2000)
<i>Cream Formation</i>	
Hydroxypropylmethylcellulose together with polyvinylpyrrolidone	Monsanto, Hooshyar, Meuldijk and Zondervan (2014)
<i>Adsorption process (Adsorbents)</i>	
Lignocellulose (cedar wood sawdust)	Sakanaka (2003)
Lignocellulose (tea stalks)	Ye et al. (2009)
Lignocellulose (fir sawdust) copolymerized with N-vinylpyrrolidone	Ye et al. (2010)
Active carbon	Ye et al. (2007)
Polyamide-6	Ye et al. (2011)
Poly(acrylamide-co-ethylene glycol dimethylacrylate)	Lu et al. (2010)
Polyvinylpolypyrrolidone	Dong et al. (2011b)
Polyvinylpolypyrrolidone	Fan et al. (2014)
<i>Membrane technology combined with adsorption process</i>	
Ultrafiltration: cellulose acetate–titanium composite membrane and polyamide resin	Li, Wang, Ma and Zhang (2005)
<i>PLE combined with SAS precipitation</i>	
Stage 1: PLE: 10 MPa, 100 °C, 20 min, ethyl lactate as solvent Stage 2: SAS: 30 MPa, 70 °C, 40 (CO ₂ /extract flow ratio)	Villanueva Bermejo et al. (2015b)

1143^amass of solvent / mass of plant material

1144

1145 **Figure captions:**

1146

1147 **Figure 1.** Chemical structure for the main catechin monomers (a) and caffeine (b)
1148 present in green tea.

1149

1150 **Figure 2.** Chemical structure of ethyl lactate

1151

1152 **Figure 1**

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1154(a)

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1159(b)

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1162

1163

1164 **Figure 2**

1165

R ¹	R ²	Compound
H	H	Epicatechin
OH	H	Epigallocatechin
H	X	Epicatechin gallate
OH	X	Epigallocatechin gallate

